

Figure Z8

Figure Z8: Cell state annotation and corresponding marker gene expression for GSE133486. (A) Cell-state marker gene expression. **(B)** White and beige adipocyte marker gene expression. **(C)** New cell state labels. A list of abbreviations used in this figure appear in the Methods.